

WOMEN DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES AND POVERTY REDUCTION: A CASE STUDY OF IKOT EKPENE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

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ABSTRACT

Women development is important in to any society that aims to achieve sustainable development. However, there are several challenges faced by women which ranges from lack of women's education, political participation, skills acquisition programs, financial empowerment. This study examined women development strategies and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. Survey research design was used in the study. Two hundred and twenty-two thousand one hundred and fifty formed the population of the study. Taro Yamene's formula was used to determine the sample size of 380, while Chi- square served as the statistical tool of the study. "Participatory empowerment theory" of Paulo Freire served as the theoretical frame work of the study. The findings recorded that women education, economic empowerment, skills acquisition and political participation, if properly institutionalized in their favour will alleviate poverty in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. The study concluded among others that by working together, we can create more just an equitable society where women and men can have equal opportunities to thrive. The study recommended, among others, that skills acquisition center in the like of Dakkada be establish in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area with resource persons drawn from the state technical school in the area to train and equip women as well as other vulnerable children with skills that will make them self-reliance.

Keywords: Women, Development, Strategies, Poverty reduction

INTRODUCTION

Poverty reduction and women's empowerment are crucial development goals globally. In Nigeria, women social-economic status is disproportionately affected by poverty. Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area is characterized by high poverty rates and gender inequality. According to the UN Women on post economic empowerment women play a vital role in the economy of the society by educating, developing and empowering them helps the society to achieve sustainable development goals (UN Women, 2024). It also creates job opportunities, encourage women involvement in leadership and increase women participation in decisions making of the society. The economic value of the society is impacted by the active participation of the population in labour market. Women which makes about 49.7% of the world's population have a participation of less than 50% in the labour market across various countries currently, one out of every women is living in extreme poverty and according to report, it will get worse by 2030 (UN Women, 2024). It is evidence that empowering women economically, socially and politically contributes significantly to poverty alleviation and sustainable development. However, in some religion of developing countries women contribute to face multifaceted challenges that hinders their development opportunities and perpetuate poverty cycles (Ufot-Akpabio, 2020).

In Nigeria, there is high poverty among women despite possessing natural resources and agricultural potential, several factors contribute to this situation including traditional gender roles, limited access to education, skills training, and inadequate support system for female entrepreneurs. These factors are caused by cultural norms, discriminatory practices and inadequate policy framework that forbid women participating in decisions making sphere, exacerbating their marginalization and hindering their potential to contribute meaningfully to community development (Ufot-Akpabio, 2020).

According to World Bank (2020), poverty headcount in Nigeria is highest in rural areas, where 73% of the population lives. Women are disproportionately affected with limited access to education, healthcare, and economic opportunities (UNDP, 2019). Empowering women economically, for instance, through skills training, microfinance programs, and access to markets, not only enhances their livelihoods but also has a multiplier effect on poverty reduction within communities. Similarly, investing in girl's education ensures a more knowledgeable and skilled workforce in the future leading to higher incomes and improved living standard addressing gender disparities and promoting women's rights and fundamental pillars of sustainable and poverty reduction efforts. These strategies recognize that empowering women is just a matter of justice and equality but also a strategic imperative for achieving broader societal progress and prosperity.

In Akwa Ibom State where Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area is located, women's empowerment is critical for poverty reduction (Akwa Ibom State Government, 2018). Women development strategies such as Microfinance initiatives and skills training have been implemented to address poverty reduction in the area. However, the effectiveness of these strategies in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area remains understudied. This research aims to fill the knowledge gap by exploring women development strategies and their impact on poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

Women development is important to any society that wants to achieve sustainable growth. It increases women participation, grows the economy, and improve the standard of living in the society. However, women are faced with factors like political and economic problems which prevent them from contributing positivity to the society. This has increased the poverty rate and crippled the growth of the society. In Ikot Ekpene Local Government

Area, Akwa Ibom State, women are mostly affected by poverty due to various structural and systemic barriers, these barriers include limited access to education, healthcare, financial resources and economic opportunities, as well as cultural and social norms that prevent women's roles and contributions (Maurice Akpan, Okogi, 2001).

There are existing empowerment programs to mitigate these challenges but these initiatives often fail to adequately address the specific needs and challenges faced by women in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. This challenges hinders women's ability to contribute meaningfully to their families, communities, and the local economy, perpetuating cycles of poverty and undermining sustainable development in the area (Maurice A. Okgi, 2001). Thus, there is a need to evaluate strategies and propose possible solutions to address the prevalent poverty rate in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to examine women development strategies and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. Specifically, the study aims to :

- i. To examine the impact of women's education on poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.
- ii. To find out the impact of women's participation in politics on poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.
- iii. To determine if women's financial empowerment has impacted on poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

HYPOTHESES

This study hypothesizes that:

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant relationship between the impact of women's education and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant relationship between the impact of women's participation in politics and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant relationship between skills acquisition programs for women and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Women's Development Strategies

Women's development is a global issue, with both rural and urban women facing unique challenges. According to the United Nations (2020), women make up 43% of the global agricultural workforce, with many rural women engaged in subsistence farming. Rural women face challenges such as limited access to education, healthcare, and economic opportunities (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2020). In contrast, urban women face challenges such as gender-based violence, limited access to affordable housing, and unequal pay (UN Women, 2020). Despite these challenges, women globally are driving change through activism, entrepreneurship, and leadership (World Bank, 2020). In rural areas, women are leading initiatives such as sustainable agriculture and natural resource management (International Fund for Agricultural Development, 2020).

Urban women are leading initiatives such as gender-responsive urban planning and women's economic empowerment programs. Technology is also playing a crucial role in

empowering women globally, with initiatives such as mobile banking and digital literacy programs (GSMA, 2020). However, women still face significant barriers to accessing technology, including limited internet access and digital skills (ITU, 2020). Global policies such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) also play a crucial role in promoting women's development (United Nations, 2020). Women's development is a global issue requiring a comprehensive approach that addresses the unique challenges faced by both rural and urban women.

Women's development in Africa has made significant progress in recent years, with various initiatives aimed at empowering women and promoting gender equality. According to the African Development Bank (2020), women's economic empowerment is crucial for Africa's development, with women accounting for 70% of the informal sector. Education is also essential for women's development in Africa, with initiatives such as the African Girls' Education Initiative (2020) aimed at improving girls' access to quality education. In addition, healthcare is a critical aspect of women's development, with initiatives such as the African Union's Campaign for Accelerated Reduction of Maternal Mortality aimed at reducing maternal mortality.

Women's political empowerment is also on the rise in Africa, with initiatives such as the African Women's Leadership Network (2020) aimed at promoting women's leadership and participation in decision-making processes. Despite progress, women in Africa still face significant challenges, including gender-based violence, limited access to land and resources, and discriminatory laws and policies (UN Women, 2020). To address these challenges, the African Union has launched initiatives such as the African Union's Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment Strategy (2020) aimed at promoting gender equality and women's empowerment.

Women's development in Africa requires sustained efforts and commitments from governments, civil society, and individuals to address the unique challenges faced by women and promote gender equality. Education and skills development are crucial strategies for women's empowerment and development in Nigeria. According to the World Bank (2019), education can help women break the cycle of poverty and improve their socio-economic status. In Nigeria, women's access to quality education is limited, particularly in rural areas. The National Commission for Mass Literacy (2020) reports that over 40% of Nigerian women are illiterate, highlighting the need for literacy programs. Vocational training programs can also enhance women's skills and competencies, increasing their employability and economic independence. The National Board for Technical Education (2020) offers various vocational training programs for women in Nigeria. STEM education (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) is also essential for women's development in Nigeria. The Federal Ministry of Education (2020) has implemented initiatives to promote STEM education among Nigerian girls and women. Entrepreneurship development programs can also empower women in Nigeria. The Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (2020) provides training and support for women entrepreneurs. According to UN Women (2020), women's participation in decision-making processes is critical for gender equality and women's empowerment. Education and skills development can increase women's confidence and capacity to participate in decision-making. UNICEF (2019) highlights the importance of gender equality and women's empowerment in Nigeria. Education and skills development can challenge gender stereotypes and societal norms, promoting gender equality. Economically women

development strategies aim to promote gender equality and empower women economically. These strategies can be explained through various economic theories and concepts.

Poverty Reduction

Poverty reduction in the context of women's development in Nigeria refers to the efforts aimed at improving the socio-economic status of women, who are often the most vulnerable to poverty. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2020), women in Nigeria are more likely to live in poverty than men, with a poverty rate of 45.8% compared to 38.2% for men. Initiatives such as the National Social Safety Nets Project (2020) and the Conditional Cash Transfer Programme (2020) have been implemented to provide financial support to poor and vulnerable women. Microfinance programme, such as the Central Bank of Nigeria's microfinance initiative (2020), also target women, providing them with access to financial services and training to start or expand their businesses. Agricultural development programme, like the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development's initiatives (2020), aim to improve women's productivity and income through training and provision of inputs. Education and skills development programme, such as the Federal Ministry of Education's initiatives (2020), focus on empowering women with skills to improve their livelihoods. The National Poverty Reduction with Growth Strategy (2020) also recognizes the importance of addressing women's poverty and has incorporated strategies to promote their economic empowerment.

Poverty can be located within the context of contradiction between the resources available to an individual and the demand and condition of his/her environment. Poverty is a dreaded condition of absence of capacity to maintain, at least, basic level of decent living. It is a hydra-headed condition which tends to restrict people from socio-economic opportunities. As a complex and multi-dimensional phenomenon, poverty goes beyond the condition of lack of resources. It extends to social inequality, insecurity, illiteracy, poor health, as well as restricted or total lack of opportunities for personal growth and self-realization (Mboho and Ekaette, 2018). Asuquo, Bassey, Samuel, Daniel and Usoroh (2022) posited that as many people have difficulty in finding jobs in the formal economic sectors, informal sector provides earning opportunity and livelihoods for operators to support the dependent members of their family such as siblings, children and old parents.

Poverty can drive people into frivolous acts. According to Udoh and Udousoro (2014), an educated person who is unemployed and idle could be exposed to violence prone activities such as armed robbery, raping, kidnapping, suicide and prostitution. As observed by Udoh(2012), the gap in the standard of living, particularly in terms of access to public goods is much wider than the already deplorable gaps in employment and income. This has caused poverty in our society.

Women's Education and Poverty Reduction

Women's education is a critical component in the fight against poverty. Research has consistently shown that educating women has a positive impact on their economic outcomes, health, and empowerment (UNESCO, 2019). In fact, a study by the World Bank (2018) found that every additional year of schooling for girls reduces the likelihood of poverty by 8.9%. This is because education increases women's earning potential, improves their productivity, and enhances their ability to secure better-paying jobs (Psacharopoulos and Patrinos, 2018).

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) emphasizes that education empowers women by increasing their earning potential and

enabling them to participate in decision-making processes that affect their lives and communities. By investing in girls' education, societies can achieve a more knowledgeable and skilled workforce, leading to economic growth and poverty reduction. Moreover, women's education has a ripple effect on their families and communities. Educated women are more likely to invest in their children's education and health, leading to improved outcomes for the next generation (UNICEF, 2019). A study published in the *Journal of Development Economics* (2018) found that educated women are more likely to participate in the labor force, have greater control over household resources, and make informed decisions about their reproductive health.

Since Nigeria gained independence from British rule in 1960, education sector in the country has struggled with persistent barriers ranging from gender inequality, lack of resources, and inadequate infrastructure among other deteriorating factors (Udoh, 2025). Furthermore, education empowers women to challenge societal norms and gender stereotypes, leading to greater autonomy and decision-making power (Kabeer, 2018). A study by the *International Journal of Educational Development* (2015) highlighted that women's education can lead to improved health outcomes, including reduced child mortality rates and improved nutrition. In addition, women's education can have a positive impact on economic growth and poverty reduction at the macro level. A study by the McKinsey Global Institute (2015) found that if women's participation in the labor force were to increase by 10%, GDP could increase by up to 3%.

According to Samuel, Asuquo, Thompson and Nya (2023), Women's education is very important for the development of our communities, States, nations, and key to the achievement of global sustainable development. But some don't appreciate women education instead, as observed by Ekanem and Asuquo (2024), these women are doubly tutored, traumatized, and exposed to very unruly treatments which compound their conditions and predispose them to an early grave. Ekanem and Asuquo (2024) posited that it is always believed that, parents are the first teachers; they should be able to form part of their children's reasoning/belief system, by inculcating and educating them with the right ideas, values, morals and dictates of the society and making known the implications of certain actions and decisions in life. Women's Education and Poverty Reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. Educating women is a powerful strategy for poverty reduction. In areas like Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area in Nigeria, enhancing women's access to education can lead to significant economic, social, and health benefits that contribute to poverty alleviation. Investing in women's education in Ikot Ekpene can lead to a transformative impact on poverty reduction. By implementing targeted strategies that enhance access to quality education, promote community awareness, and provide supportive learning environments, the local government can empower women and create a sustainable path out of poverty for the entire community (UN Women, 2020). Asuquo and Ekanem (2023) aver that when education is compromised, it becomes challenging to produce a workforce that can contribute meaningfully to various sectors, hindering economic growth and diversification. That is why female education is important.

Women's Participation in Politics and Poverty Reduction

Women's participation in politics is a crucial factor in poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. Research has consistently shown that women's involvement in decision-making processes leads to more inclusive and equitable policies, which can

address the unique needs of women and marginalized communities (Okeke-Uzodike, 2018). This is because women are more likely to prioritize issues that affect their families and communities, such as education, healthcare, and economic empowerment (Afonja, 2018). In Nigeria, women's participation in politics is still limited, with only 6.7% of seats held by women in the National Assembly (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020). However, studies have shown that increasing women's representation in politics can lead to improved healthcare, education, and economic outcomes (Afonja, 2018). For instance, a study by Eke (2017) found that women's education is a critical factor in poverty reduction in Akwa Ibom State, and that increasing women's access to education can lead to improved economic outcomes.

Ekanem, Asuquo, Ogar and Ofuka (2023) argued that, women all over the world encounter greater hurdles/hindrances in political participation. Women's participation in politics can lead to increased investment in education and healthcare, particularly for women and girls. This can result in improved literacy rates, better health outcomes, and reduced infant mortality rates. In Ikot Ekpene, women in politics can advocate for more schools, healthcare facilities, and social services, leading to improved human development outcomes, Eke (2019).

Women in politics can support initiatives that promote women's entrepreneurship, job creation, and economic empowerment. This can include training programs, microfinance initiatives, and support for women-owned businesses. In Ikot Ekpene, women in politics can help create opportunities for women to start and grow businesses, leading to increased economic activity and poverty reduction, Essien (2019). Women's participation in politics can help address gender-based violence and discrimination, which are major barriers to poverty reduction. Women in politics can advocate for policies and programs that protect women's rights, prevent violence, and promote gender equality. In Ikot Ekpene, women in politics can help create a safer and more equitable environment for women and girls, Umoette (2020). As seen by Udonwa, Effiong, Asuquo and Samuel (2022), it is a common knowledge that children of affluent homes have easy access to gainful employment as their parents provide the needed links. Children from poor background are left in the dark in pursuit of a decent job.

Women play a critical role in agriculture, but often lack access to resources and support. Women in politics can advocate for policies and programs that support women farmers, improve agricultural productivity, and increase food security. In Ikot Ekpene, women in politics can help improve agricultural practices, increase access to markets, and reduce hunger and malnutrition, Udo (2019). Women's participation in politics can lead to increased investment in community development and social welfare programs, such as social protection schemes, water and sanitation projects, and community infrastructure. In Ikot Ekpene, women in politics can help create more livable and sustainable communities, leading to improved quality of life and poverty reduction (Ekpo, 2018).

Women's Financial Empowerment and Poverty Reduction

Women's financial empowerment is a crucial factor in poverty reduction, as it enables women to increase their income and assets, improve their financial literacy and decision-making, access credit and financial services, start and grow businesses, and reduce their vulnerability to poverty and economic shocks (IFC, 2019). Research has shown that women's financial empowerment can lead to reduced poverty and income inequality (IFC, 2019). A study by the World Bank (2019) found that women's financial empowerment is

associated with improved health and education outcomes, as women are more likely to invest in their families and communities. Additionally, women's financial empowerment can lead to increased economic growth and development, as women are more likely to start and grow businesses, creating jobs and stimulating economic activity (WEF, 2019).

Moreover, women's financial empowerment can enhance women's autonomy and decision-making, as women are more likely to have control over financial resources and make decisions about their own lives (CGAP, 2018). This, in turn, can lead to reduced gender-based violence and discrimination, as women are more likely to have the economic resources and independence to leave abusive relationships and pursue their own goals and aspirations (UN Women, 2020). Women's financial empowerment is a critical factor in poverty reduction, as it enables women to improve their economic outcomes, increase their autonomy and decision-making, and reduce their vulnerability to poverty and economic shocks.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Participatory Empowerment Theory

The Participatory Empowerment Theory is an approach that emphasizes the importance of individuals and communities taking an active role in their own empowerment and development. This theory is based on the idea that people have the capacity to identify their own needs and develop strategies to address those need (Chambers, 1997). It also recognizes that empowerment is a long-term process that requires sustained effort, commitment, and support (Alsop and Heinsohn, 2005). Participatory empowerment theory is centered on the concept of participation, which involves the active engagement of individuals and communities in decision-making processes and development initiatives (Freire, 1970). This approach recognizes that individuals and communities have the right to participate in decisions that affect their lives and that their participation is essential for achieving empowerment and poverty reduction (Kabeer, 2005).

The theory also emphasizes the importance of critical consciousness and collective action in achieving empowerment (Rowlands, 1997). Critical consciousness involves the ability to analyze and understand the social, economic, and political structures that contribute to poverty and disempowerment, while collective action involves working together to address these issues and achieve positive change. The Participatory Empowerment Theory offers a nuanced understanding of empowerment as a multifaceted and context-specific concept that requires the active participation and engagement of individuals and communities.

Assumptions of Participatory Empowerment Theory

The Participatory Empowerment Theory assumes that empowerment is a process that occurs when individuals or groups gain control over their lives, resources, and decisions that affect them (Freire, 1970). This theory posits that empowerment is not a product of external intervention, but rather an iterative process of self-discovery, critical consciousness, and collective action (Rowlands, 1997). The theory assumes that individuals and communities have the capacity to identify their own needs and develop strategies to address them (Chambers, 1997). It also assumes that empowerment is a long-term process that requires sustained effort, commitment, and support (Alsop and Heinsohn, 2005). Furthermore, the Participatory Empowerment Theory assumes that gender-based discrimination and inequality are significant barriers to empowerment and poverty reduction (Kabeer, 2005).

Therefore, addressing these issues is essential for achieving empowerment and poverty reduction.

Application of the Theory to the Study

The Participatory Empowerment Theory has been applied to women's development strategies and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area through various initiatives. One such initiative is the establishment of women's groups and cooperatives, which provide a platform for women to participate in decision-making processes and economic activities (Chambers, 1997). These groups have enabled women to access credit facilities, training, and markets, thereby reducing poverty and improving their livelihoods (Kabeer, 2005).

Another application of the Participatory Empowerment Theory is the implementation of gender-sensitive policies and programs, which address the unique needs and challenges faced by women in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area (Alsop and Heinsohn, 2005). For instance, the local government has established programs to support women's entrepreneurship, education, and healthcare, which have contributed to women's empowerment and poverty reduction (Rowlands, 1997). Furthermore, the Participatory Empowerment Theory has been applied through the use of participatory approaches to development, which involve women in the identification of their own needs and the development of strategies to address them (Freire, 1970). This approach has ensured that women's development strategies are context-specific and responsive to the needs of women in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

METHODOLOGY

For the study on “Women Development Strategy and Poverty Reduction: A Case Study of Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.”, survey design was an appropriate choice. Survey design is a type of research design that involves collecting data from a large group of people, usually through questionnaires or interviews. It is used when the goal is to gather standardized information from respondents about their attitudes, behaviors, or characteristics. Surveys are typically employed in social science research to collect data from a sample that represents a larger population, allowing researchers to generalize their findings. This design combines both quantitative and qualitative approaches, allowing the researcher to gather comprehensive data on the subject matter

The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula. The sample size of the study was 399. Simple random sampling is a fundamental sampling technique where every individual within the population has an equal and independent chance of being selected. This method was employed to ensure that the sample size drawn for the study truly represent the larger population, and minimizing bias in the selection process. In this study, simple random sampling was used to select respondents from the population of women in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

The data gathered from the instruments were analyzed using simple percentages and chi-square. Chi-square can be analyzed as this:

$$X^2 = \frac{\sum(F_o - F_e)^2}{F_e}$$

RESULT

The analysis of the socio-demographic characteristics indicates that 130 respondent representing 34.2% were Male while 250 respondent representing 65.8% were Female who responded to the questionnaire. 30 respondents representing 7.9% where under 20 of age, 70 respondent representing 18.4% where aged 21-26,50 respondent representing 13.2% where aged 26-40, 150 respondent representing 39.5% where aged 41-50, while 80 respondents representing 21.0% were aged 50 and above. 200 respondents representing 52.6% where of no educational level, 90 respondent representing 23.6% where of primary education, 50 respondent representing 13.2% where of secondary education, 20 respondent representing 5.3% where of tertiary education, while 20 respondents representing 5.3% where of Ph.D and above. 20 respondents representing 5.3% where single, 180 respondent representing 47.4% where married, 40 respondent representing 10.5% where divorced, 140 respondent representing 36.8% where widowed. 120 respondents representing 31.6% where farmers, 140 respondent representing 36.8% where Traders, 50 respondent representing 13.2% where civil servants, 70 respondent representing 18.4% where of other occupations. 200 respondents representing 52.6% where Christian, 80 respondent representing 21.1% where Islam, 60 respondent representing 15.8% where Traditional worshippers, 40 respondent representing 10.5% of other religion.

Hypotheses One

There is no significant relationship between the impact of women's education and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

Table 1: Responses from Question one was used to test hypotheses one.

Responses category	SA	A	SD	D	TOTAL
Women education	100	70	20	18	208
Poverty reduction	106	26	20	20	172
Total	206	96	40	38	380

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2.1: Chi-Square Distribution Table

Cell	Fo	Fe	Fo - Fe	(Fo - Fe) ²	$\frac{(Fo - fe)^2}{Fe}$
A	100	112.75	-12.75	162.56	1.44
B	70	52.54	17.46	304.85	5.80
C	20	21.89	-1.89	3.57	0.16
D	18	20.8	-2.8	7.84	0.37
E	106	93.24	12.76	162.81	1.74
F	26	43.45	-17.45	304.50	7.00
G	20	18.10	1.9	3.61	0.19
H	20	17.2	2.8	7.84	0.45
					$\sum x^2 = 17.15$

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Degree of freedom} &= (R-1)(C-1) \\ &= (2-1)(4-1) \\ &= 1 \times 3 \\ &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The level of significance} &= 0.05 \\ \text{Calculated value} &= 17.15 \\ \text{Critical table value} &= 7.82 \end{aligned}$$

Decision: Since the calculated chi-square value of 17.15 is higher than the critical table value of 7.82 at 0.05 level of significance. Thus the Alternative hypotheses (H_1) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H_0) is therefore rejected.

From the above, it is observed that there is a significant relationship between the impact of women's education and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between the impact of women participation in politics and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

Table 3.1: Responses from Question Six (6) was used to test hypotheses two.

Responses category	SA	A	SD	D	TOTAL
Political participation	75	72	43	20	210
Poverty reduction	87	48	20	15	170
Total	162	112	63	35	380

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2.2: Chi-Square Distribution Table

Cell	Fo	Fe	Fo - Fe	(Fo - Fe) ²	$\frac{(Fo - fe)^2}{Fe}$
A	75	89.52	14.52	210.83	2.35
B	72	61.89	10.11	102.21	1.65
C	43	34.81	8.19	67.07	1.92
D	20	19.34	0.66	04.3	22.23
E	87	72.47	14.53	211.12	2.91
F	48	50.10	-2.1	4.41	88.02
G	20	28.18	-8.18	66.91	2.37
H	15	15.65	-0.65	0.42	26.85
					$\sum x^2 = 148.3$

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Degree of freedom} &= (R-1)(C-1) \\ &= (2-1)(4-1) \\ &= 1 \times 3 \\ &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The level of significance} &= 0.05 \\ \text{Calculated value} &= 148.3 \end{aligned}$$

Critical table value = 7.82

Decision: Since the calculated chi-square value of 148.3 is higher than the critical table value of 7.82 at 0.05 level of significance. Thus the Alternative hypotheses (H_1) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H_0) is therefore rejected.

From the above, it is observed that there is a significant relationship between the impact of women participation in politics and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Hypotheses one was tested using question one of the questionnaire and it revealed that there is significant relationship between the impacts of women education, thereby leading to the reduction of poverty in Ikot Ekpene. The questionnaire which was used in testing the hypothesis confirms to this as majority of respondents representing 47.4% strongly agreed that women's education is crucial for reducing poverty. In the respondent's community (Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area) the findings is consistence with the United Nations Education Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2019) which emphasizes that education empower women by increasing their earnings potential and enabling them to participate in decision making processes that affect their lives and communities. And also (UNICEF, 2019) states that educated women are more likely to invest in their children's education and health, leading to improved outcomes for the next generations.

Hypotheses two was tested using question six from the questionnaire and it revealed that women participation in politics leads to more poverty reduction initiatives in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area, thus, depicting that there is no significant relationship between the impact of women's participation in politics and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. The questionnaire which was used in testing the hypotheses confirms to this as majority of respondents representing 51.6% strongly agreed that women's participation in politics leads to more poverty reduction initiative in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. The findings are in inconsistent with Afonja (2018) which says that increasing women's representation in politics can lead to improved healthcare, education and economic outcomes.

CONCLUSION

This study examines the intricate relationship between women's development strategies and poverty reduction in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. The women's development strategies and poverty reduction initiatives in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area have shown promising results. The education and skills acquisition programs, political participation, financial empowerment, and community-based initiatives have all contributed to improving the lives of women in the area.

However, despite these efforts, poverty remains a significant challenge, and gender-based discrimination and inequality persist. Therefore, it is essential to continue and expand these initiatives, ensuring that they are tailored to the specific needs of women in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. Addressing the structural barriers that perpetuate gender-based poverty, such as limited access to resources and decision-making positions, is crucial. This requires a sustained commitment to gender main-streaming and women's empowerment from all stakeholders, including government, civil society, and community leaders.

Reducing poverty and promoting women's development in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area requires a comprehensive and inclusive approach that addresses the social, economic, and political determinants of gender-based poverty. By working together, we can create a more just and equitable society where women and men have equal opportunities to thrive.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study recommends the following actions to be taken by the government, community, and individuals to enhance women development and reduce poverty in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area;

- i. That a scholarship programme for children from vulnerable homes especially girls be instituted in the area to help them access secondary and tertiary education.
- ii. That women's caucus be established in the local government council to advocate for women's welfare and interests as well as promote gender-sensitive policies to accommodate and encourage their participation in politics.

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